

Organizational Leadership for Inclusive Learning: Insights in Public Elementary Schools

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Abstract- *Inclusive education must be implemented to ensure all learners benefit from the teaching-learning process. This study aimed to see if there was a relationship between the factors influencing Inclusive Education implementation in public elementary schools, considering organizational leadership qualities. The study used a quantitative, descriptive-predictive design involving 154 elementary school teachers and 254 parents drawn randomly from the Ambray District, Division of San Pablo City. The respondents' perceptions of organizational leadership and the implementation of inclusive education in public elementary schools were assessed using a survey questionnaire. Respondents perceived organizational leadership in inclusive education as evident, according to the mean and standard deviation. Similarly, all aspects of inclusive education implementation were perceived to be evident, such as creating an inclusive culture, developing curricula for all, and orchestrating learning.*

Furthermore, using the Pearson product-moment correlation coefficient, it was discovered that implementing inclusive education is significantly related to factors such as inclusive education organizational leadership. Similarly, these significantly predict the level of inclusive education implementation in public elementary schools. As a result, administrators should consider offering teachers inclusive education professional development activities to improve their readiness to implement inclusion in their classrooms.

Keywords- Inclusive education, organizational leadership, teachers' readiness, parental involvement

I. INTRODUCTION

Teachers and educational institutions have consistently strived to offer comprehensive education that meets the requirements of all students. Inclusive education is a progressive and imaginative educational approach focusing on the collaborative advantages individuals can derive from the teaching-learning process (Gillis & Krull, 2020). The importance of inclusive education is emphasized in the Sustainable Development Goal and the Education 2030 Framework for Action (United Nations Educational, Scientific, and Cultural Organization [UNESCO], 2016).

These documents define the principles of inclusive education and emphasize that promoting inclusion and equity in education is crucial for achieving a transformative education agenda. The commitment addresses all types of exclusion, marginalization, disparities, and inequalities in access, participation, and learning outcomes. In education, inclusion refers to providing equal opportunities for all students, with a special focus on those who are members of minority groups, originate from low-income backgrounds, and are considered vulnerable (Calgary Board of Health, 2008).

Article 14, Section 1 of the 1987 Philippine Constitution guarantees every person's right to receive a high standard education. It requires the government to implement necessary measures to ensure its accessibility to everyone. According to the 2009 Department of Education Order No. 72, inclusive education is admitting all children, regardless of their race, size, shape, color, ability, or disability, with assistance from the school, state, students, parents, and the community. The 2013 Enhanced Basic Education Act expanded the definition of conclusion to include gifted and talented children, learners with disabilities, learners of the madrasa curriculum, indigenous peoples, and learners facing challenging circumstances such as geographical isolation, chronic illness, abuse, or displacement due to armed conflict, urban resettlement, or disaster. These groups were identified as the target audience for inclusive education. Thus, teachers who can achieve inclusivity in the educational system through cultivating positive values, imparting knowledge, and fostering the development of outstanding students' talents to navigate life's obstacles emerge as the primary agents of inclusivity within the classroom.

Nevertheless, studies indicate that there is still room for improvement regarding the understanding and active participation of school administrators in implementing inclusive education (IE) (Muega, 2016). Implementers question the effectiveness of their stated approaches in meeting the demands of inclusive education at a higher level. The lack of a unified educational strategy in the country accessible to all pupils indicates that a strong conceptual foundation for inclusive education (IE) has yet to be built. The absence of a solid foundation for implementing Inclusive Education (IE) makes it difficult to determine the appropriate

level of participation that school community members should have in educating children with special needs (CSN).

The tasks, responsibilities, and style of school heads' organizational leadership are crucial factors in driving change inside a school. They play a major role in building and promoting a successful inclusion program (Cohen, 2015). Inclusive education entails using the inclusion approach to establish a novel form of education that integrates students with disabilities into regular school classrooms (Jackson et al., 2000). Inclusive schools integrate students with special needs into regular classrooms, enabling them to engage and associate with their classmates in mainstream education (Hussain, 2017). All pupils get substantial, demanding, and suitable educational components and distinct instructional approaches catering to their abilities and requirements (Khaleel et al., 2021). Although the Philippines has previously implemented an inclusion policy, many schoolteachers still do not fully recognize the significance of inclusive education (Muega & Echavia, 2011).

In addition, although policies advocate for inclusive education, school administrators face complexities and difficulties in attaining this objective (Hoppey and McLeskey, 2013). To strive toward this objective, it was proposed that school principals be held responsible for overseeing and coordinating their schools and fostering an inclusive educational environment for all students. Principals must assume multiple duties to guarantee that their schools can provide professional assistance to teachers and other educators.

This study relates to the four selected overarching topics of the Department of Education's Basic Education Research Agenda, notably theme 3-Inclusive Education. This also emphasizes the national institution's responsibility to deliver high-quality primary education to all Filipinos, guaranteeing that educational goals are met by optimizing instructors' skills and the abilities of all students. For inclusion to be effectively implemented, engaging different stakeholders in the process is imperative. All stakeholders, including students, parents, the community, teachers, specialists, and educational leaders, should wholeheartedly adopt and execute the principle of inclusion (Bublitz, 2016; Hatch, 2018). Collaboration among stakeholders is vital to uphold the rights of students with disabilities, who have long struggled to attain equitable educational opportunities comparable to their non-disabled counterparts. This study aimed to investigate the impact of organizational leadership on implementing inclusive education policies in public elementary schools. The goal was to provide valuable insights and recommendations for

improving policies and guiding individuals involved in implementing inclusive education.

Background of the Study. The recognition of inclusion in education as an activity influenced by social, cultural, and material factors and evolving via social interactions involving various interconnected individuals and activities is gaining widespread acceptance. It addresses the challenges that come as a result of the pupils' variety. The objective is to formulate a suitable policy for educational programs and establish a conducive environment, ethos, and methodologies inside the school unit to become an inclusive institution that offers equitable opportunities for studying and teaching.

Inclusive education aims to overhaul educational systems, cultures, practices, and school organizations to effectively address the different educational requirements of students so that every child may attain optimal learning outcomes and full participation. Increased inclusivity in schools correlates with higher student enrollment rates and reduced student exclusion rates (White, 2008). This pertains to Sustainable Development Goal 4 (SDG 4), which emphasizes the significance of inclusive education and urges countries to implement a plan of action to ensure that children with perceived differences are included and treated fairly in the education system. Inclusion emphasizes the potential for equitable participation of individuals with disabilities (including physical, social, and emotional difficulties) in regular education settings whenever feasible. However, it still allows for individual choices and provides options for specific assistance and accommodations for individuals who require it (UNESCO, 2021).

UNESCO is currently focused on the 2030 agenda for sustainable development. However, certain challenges arise, such as determining the right balance between short-term and long-term actions to promote inclusiveness without sacrificing quality. The first obstacle would be implementing a thorough assessment and feedback system that consistently assesses the effectiveness of the inclusion-focused training programs and promptly addresses the unfulfilled requirements of all teachers.

In the Philippines, inclusive education seeks to integrate children with special needs into a flexible learning environment, enabling them to receive high-quality education that maximizes their potential for comprehensive development (Dela Fuente, 2021). This statement upholds the principles of the 1987 Philippine Constitution, which guarantees the right to receive education of a high standard for every individual and requires the government to implement necessary measures to

ensure its availability to all citizens (Article 14, Section 1). The state must create a comprehensive education system designed to meet the demands of the population (as stated in Article 14, Section 2).

The Department of Education (DepEd) is the governmental entity entrusted with the responsibility of safeguarding and advancing the entitlement of every Filipino citizen to a superior standard of education, which would empower each student to achieve their maximum capabilities and actively engage in the nation's development. The Department of Education (DepEd) has enacted the 2013 Enhanced Basic Education Act to implement this constitutional right. This law emphasizes the importance of providing education tailored to all learners' needs, cognitive abilities, cultural backgrounds, circumstances, and diversity. It aims to achieve this through targeted programs. To promote inclusivity, the K to 12-education system has expanded its objectives in response to the diverse circumstances of students and their families. This is achieved by offering more choices to prepare them for higher education and work or entrepreneurial prospects. The K to 12 curriculum additionally supports implementing programs that cater to learners' unique physical, intellectual, psychological, and cultural needs in various circumstances. These initiatives are based on inclusion, a fundamental aspect of the Enhanced Basic Education Program (DepEd Order No. 43, s. 2013).

The 2015 Education Plan reiterates the comprehensive nature of inclusive education as the guiding principle for universal education policy and planning framework. This objective is contingent upon various elements, such as the structure of the educational institution, legal regulations, policies and initiatives, management, educational settings, curriculum and teaching resources, implementers, school administrators, educators, and others with a vested interest in the school.

The idea of inclusion advocates for institutions to be sensitive and responsive to the characteristics, circumstances, and actualities of learners in our country. The Department is instructed to proactively tackle these issues by incorporating them into the curriculum and implementing additional interventions. K to 12 implements Inclusive Education, a policy approach that focuses on creating and executing learner-centered and context-responsive programs.

Upon investigation of the researcher's area, it was found that Ambray District in the Division of San Pablo City is the only school district out of the seven with a specialized school specifically designed to serve children with special needs in the city and surrounding communities. This indicates

that it cannot meet the requirements of all pupils with special needs, resulting in their integration into the general education system. Therefore, it is crucial to provide a solid basis for other schools, encompassing infrastructure, administration, and educators, to effectively address the requirements of learners with special educational needs in a regular classroom environment. This will exemplify the DepEd's objective of advocating and safeguarding the entitlement of every Filipino to a standard, fair, culturally rooted, and comprehensive elementary education.

Nevertheless, several public schools in both urban and rural locations must be well-furnished (Salapare, 2016). One possible explanation for the skepticism of numerous general education teachers in the Philippines over their ability to teach in an inclusive school is the following. Research has indicated that currently employed teachers are eager to collaborate and cooperate with specialists to incorporate students with communication and sensory needs (CSN) into regular education classrooms. Furthermore, it has emphasized their inadequate readiness to accommodate pupils with disorders or disabilities (Muega & Echavia, 2011). This possibility may also apply to the public school teachers in Ambray and the Division of San Pablo City. This study seeks to investigate the preparedness of public primary schools to implement inclusive education methods, including the characteristics that may be significantly correlated with its execution, such as organizational leadership.

Research Questions. This study determined whether a relationship exists among the factors influencing Inclusive Education implementation in public elementary schools. It determined the extent by which specific variables on organizational leadership predict the level of implementation of inclusive education in Ambray District, Division of San Pablo City, during the school year 2022-2023.

Specifically, it aimed to answer the following questions:

1. How do the respondents perceive the level of organizational leadership in inclusive education in terms of:
 1. Leadership Roles and Responsibilities; and,
 2. Transformational Leadership Practices?
2. How do the respondents perceive School Readiness for Inclusive Education as to:
 - a. Creating Inclusive Culture
 - b. Constructing Curricula for all Learning; and
 - c. Orchestrating Learning?
3. Is there a significant relationship between organizational leadership in public elementary schools and the implementation of inclusive education?

4. Does organizational leadership predict the level of inclusive education implementation?

II. METHODOLOGY

Research Design. This study employed a quantitative method and a non-experimental research design with a descriptive-predictive approach. Johnson (2001) suggests that non-experimental research, like the current study, involves describing phenomena and documenting its characteristics without modifying any variables in the study.

To provide a clearer understanding of the design, Johnson (2001) categorized non-experimental research into two distinct dimensions, namely purpose and duration. This study is classified as explanatory in terms of its purpose dimension. The term "explanatory" denotes the research's primary objective of elucidating rather than merely describing the phenomena under investigation. The main objective is to elucidate the functioning of certain phenomena and the underlying reasons for conducting experimental tests to validate a theory. It answers the question of comprehending the functioning or underlying motivations of something. The present study utilized a cross-sectional design, collecting data from research participants at a specific time and among various respondents or participants.

This study is prognostic. It attempts to make predictions about something that has not been previously attempted, tested, or recommended by analyzing existing events, policies, or other things. It frequently inquires about the functionality or effectiveness of something, as well as the potential consequences it may have.

Respondents of the Study. The study participants were comprised of elementary educators and parents residing in Ambray District, Division of San Pablo City. The district consists of ten schools with a total of 188 teachers. A random selection procedure was employed to select 154 teachers and 254 parents.

Instrument of the Study. The necessary data to investigate the study inquiries were collected through a comprehensive five-part questionnaire.

The initial section aims to collect data regarding the respondents' profiles, encompassing age, gender, marital status, highest level of schooling completed, and length of service. The second component of the instrument collected data on several facets of organizational leadership in inclusive education, including duties and responsibilities and attributes associated with transformational leadership. The survey

instrument on inclusive education implementation in public primary schools consists of three dimensions: fostering an inclusive culture, developing inclusive curricula, and coordinating learning activities.

The dimensions for the variables were determined by doing a factor analysis with a rotated component matrix. The determination of sample size for factor analysis was led by a widely used criterion stating that a KMO value of 0.6 or higher is appropriate. If the KMO value is less than 0.5, it suggests that the sample size is insufficient for factor analysis. Conversely, KMO values above 0.5 indicate that factor analysis would be suitable. The current investigation yielded a Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) value of .898 for organizational leadership.

The respondents' perceptions were evaluated using a Likert scale ranging from 1 to 5, with 5 representing the highest and 1 representing the lowest. These instruments have been modified and subjected to expert validation to assure the accuracy of the concept. Similarly, it has undergone pilot testing and an assessment of internal consistency using Cronbach's alpha to confirm its dependability.

Data Gathering Procedure. The conduct of the study was divided into three (3) phases: pre-survey phase, survey phase, and post-survey phase.

Pre-survey phase. The researcher assembled the research instruments employed in the investigation. The instruments underwent adaptation and were tested for content validity and reliability. Factor analysis was utilized to condense a substantial number of variables into smaller factors by isolating their shared characteristics. Once all the instruments were ready, the researcher sought authorization to carry out the study by submitting a letter to the College Dean. In addition, an official request letter was sent to the division superintendent of San Pablo City to seek endorsement before distributing the survey questionnaires via Google Forms.

Survey phase. The study was done in the second quarter of the academic year 2022-2023, from February to March 2023. The researcher disseminated the survey forms to the principals of the 10 schools in the Ambray District.

Post-survey phase. The data collected from the survey was inputted into the data matrix. After being reviewed by the statistician and the consultant, the data was subsequently sent to the statistical center for proper analysis. The statistical analysis and interpretation were conducted on the results obtained from the statistical center.

Statistical Treatment of Data. The study utilized descriptive and inferential statistics to address the research questions. The mean and standard deviations were employed to depict the level of organizational leadership practice, teacher readiness, parental involvement, and implementation of inclusive education in public elementary schools, as perceived

by the respondents. Conversely, the Pearson product-moment correlation coefficient (r) assessed meaningful associations between variables. Simultaneously, multiple regression analysis was utilized to ascertain the predicted correlation between the independent and dependent variables.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1. Perceived Organizational Leadership in Inclusive Education as to Roles and Responsibilities

<i>Our school/My child's school</i>	Mean	SD	VI
1. secure funding and/or resources for teachers to support best practices in inclusive education. (<i>naghaanap ng pondo/mapagkukunan ng pangsuporta sa mga pinakamahuhusay na kasanayan/gawain sa inclusive education ng mga guro</i>)	3.75	1.278	A
2. seeks mutual support and guidance from other schools or district when there are questions or concern about inclusive education programs in our school. (<i>nakikipagtulungan sa ibang mga paaralan kapag mayroong mga suliranin o isyung may kinalaman sa inclive education</i>)	3.85	1.279	A
3. has a culture shaped by vision for inclusion in instruction and learning. (<i>may kulturang hinabi mula sa vision ng inclusive na pagtuturo at pagkatuto</i>)	3.84	1.260	A
4. collaborate with stakeholders to discuss various aspects of the inclusive education program. (<i>nakikipagtulungan sa mga stakeholders ukol sa mga aspetong my kinalaman sa inclusive education</i>)	3.90	1.257	A
5. has a mechanism to monitor student assessment data to ensure they are making appropriate academic progress. (<i>may mga pamamaraang ginagamit upanag matiyak na nagkakaroon ng angkop na antas ng pagkatuto ang bawat mag-aaral</i>)	3.93	1.275	A
6. provides relevant, meaningful, and applicable professional development opportunities to teachers that focus on best practices in inclusive education. (<i>nagbibigay sa mga guro ng makabuluhan at naangkop na gawaing may kinalaman sa mga pinakamahuhusay na kasanayan sa inclusive education</i>)	3.94	1.246	A
7. allow teachers to collaborate for the purpose of coteaching. (<i>binibigyan ng pagkakataon ang mga guro na magtulungan sa mga gawaing my kinalaman sa inclusive education</i>)	4.00	1.254	A
8. holds positive perceptions toward inclusive education. (<i>mayroong positibong pananaw sa inclusive education</i>)	4.01	1.268	A
9. hold IEP meetings for all students with disabilities in our school. (<i>nagsasagawa ng mga pagpupulong sa IEP para sa lahat ng mga mag-aaral na may kapansanan sa paaralan</i>)	3.79	1.271	A
Overall	3.89	1.197	A

Legend: VI–Verbal Interpretation 5.0-4.50 Strongly Agree (Very Evident) 4.49-3.50 Agree (Evident) 3.45-2.50 Neither Agree nor Disagree (Evident to a little extent) 2.45-1.50 Disagree (Evident to a little extent) 1.45 -1.0 Strongly Disagree (Not Evident)

Table 1 analyzes the perceived organizational leadership about roles and duties in inclusive education. The study revealed that the schools surveyed have favorable attitudes towards inclusive education, with a mean score of 4.01 and a standard deviation of 1.268. Therefore, the evidence suggests that school heads are effectively fulfilling their tasks and obligations as leaders in the field of IE. These findings indicate that the schools had a favorable disposition towards inclusive education, a crucial factor in establishing a nurturing atmosphere for students with varying requirements. Furthermore, the respondents believe that the schools offer professional development opportunities to teachers pertinent,

significant, and applicable to the most effective methods in inclusive education (mean=3.94, SD=1.246). It may be inferred from this that the schools are dedicated to ensuring that their teachers have the knowledge and abilities to assist children with various needs effectively. The Department specifically ensures that professors attend faculty development activities, including seminars, training workshops, and conferences, with the intention of increasing their capabilities. As an example, the Learning Action Cell is being implemented monthly as a School-Based Continuing Professional Development Strategy for the Improvement of Teaching and Learning under the K to 12 Basic Education

Program. This initiative aims to ensure that all teaching personnel of DepEd participate in a professional learning community, which will assist them in enhancing their teaching methods and, consequently, improving learner achievement.

In addition, the Midyear In-Service Training is conducted annually to consistently improve and strengthen the skills and abilities of both teaching and non-teaching staff. Furthermore, the study also found that schools actively promote collaboration among teachers for co-teaching, with a mean score of 4.00 and a standard deviation of 1.254. This approach is widely regarded as one of the most efficient methods to promote inclusive education, as it enables teachers to exchange their knowledge and assist one another in addressing the varied requirements of their pupils. This discovery suggests that the schools acknowledge the significance of collaboration and the exchange of exemplary methods.

Nevertheless, it is crucial to examine statement 1, which received the lowest average agreement and indicated that the school obtains financing and resources to assist teachers in implementing effective strategies for inclusive education (mean=3.75, SD=1.278). This implies that the teachers require financial resources to facilitate the effective adoption of optimal strategies in inclusive education. One of the difficulties in implementing inclusive education is allocating funds from the Maintenance and Other Operating Expenses (MOOE). During the annual budget preparation, the budget for inclusive education is often neglected due to more immediate problems that require funding, such as bills and utilities. However, this lack of prioritization can hinder the overall operation of inclusive education. These expenses encompass utility bills for energy and water, internet and communication services, and remuneration for task order employees. To address these inevitable problems, school administrators and educators may seek assistance from people and non-governmental organizations through sponsorships. These sponsorships often provide financial and material

resources to promote the implementation of inclusive education in schools. Occasionally, philanthropic benefactors generously contribute educational materials for those with disabilities, including books, furniture, and financial assistance for facility renovations.

Furthermore, the respondents perceive a need to further work on conducting the IEP meetings for all students with disabilities in their respective schools (mean=3.79, SD=1.271). This implies that holding orientation in using an Individualized Educational Plan (IEP) must be intensified for the students to be aware of their current academic status and understand its importance, that is, to ensure that they are receiving appropriate specialized instruction and services. Given that the purpose of the IEP is to assist instructors in monitoring students' advancement towards specific educational objectives, the teacher must collaborate closely with both the child's parents and, whenever feasible, the child themselves to complete the IEP. Hence, it is recommended that the school consider establishing a diverse team consisting of educators, healthcare professionals, and social workers, in addition to the existing school staff and parents. The school leader will be responsible for exploring methods to enhance the abilities of these team members.

The study's findings suggest that organizational leadership in inclusive education, specifically in the roles and responsibilities aspect, was evident, with some areas needing strengthening. The schools are trying to support teachers and students to ensure that inclusive education is effectively implemented by establishing a positive perception towards inclusion and encouraging teacher collaboration in delivering quality instruction. However, it would help if additional funding sources to support teachers' IE implementation could be identified.

Table 2. Perceived Organizational Leadership in Inclusive Education as to **Transformational Leadership Practices**

<i>Our school/My child's school.. / Ang aming paaralan... /Ang paaralan ng aking anak ay...</i>	Mean	SD	VI
1. has set of values and vision that guides the decision-making process of the school heads and teachers. (<i>may set ng mga pagpapahalaga at pananaw na gumagabay sa proseso ng paggawa ng desisyon ng mga pinuno at guro ng paaralan.</i>)	3.94	1.216	A
2. promotes trust and respect within the organization. (<i>nagsusulong ng tiwala at respeto sa organisasyon</i>)	4.02	1.210	A
3. encourage teachers to seek advice from school heads. (<i>humihikayat sa mga guro na humingi ng payo sa mga pinuno ng paaralan.</i>)	4.01	1.205	A
4. challenges teachers to think about old problems in new ways. (<i>humahamon sa mga guro upang humanap ng makabagong solusyon sa mga suliranin</i>)	3.95	1.201	A
5. instill leadership among all its teachers by seeking opportunities for everyone	4.00	1.191	A

	to develop their leadership skills. (<i>nililinang ang kakayahan ng bawat isa na maging pinuno sa pamamagitan nang pagbibigay oportunidad sa bawat isa na mapaunlad pa ang kanilang mga sariling kakayahan</i>)			
6.	encourages the use of language that inspires teachers to achieve the school's vision for instruction and learning. (<i>humihikayat sa paggamit ng mga salitang nakakapagbigay inspirasyon sa mga guro upang makamit ang vision ng paaralan sa pagtuturo at pagkatuto</i>)	4.02	1.198	A
7.	challenges teachers to evoke better ideas from problems and questions. (<i>humahamon sa mga guro na pumukaw ng magagandang kaisipan mula sa mga suliranin at katanungan.</i>)	3.99	1.204	A
8.	practices leadership by example. (<i>nagpapakita ng pamumuno sa pamamagitan ng pagbibigay ng mabuting halimbawa</i>)	4.03	1.205	A
9.	provides individualized support to teachers depending on their needs. (<i>nagbibigay ng indibidwal na suporta sa bawat guro basa sa kanilang pangangailangan</i>)	4.00	1.194	A
10.	uses a variety of methods to support teachers in different ways such as mentorship, coaching, observations, and professional development activities. (<i>gumagamit ng iba't-ibang pamamaraan upang matulungang mapaunlad ang kasanayan ng mga guro katulad ng mentorship, coaching, obserbasyon, at iba pang gawaing nakalilinang ng kakayahang pangguro.</i>)	4.00	1.196	A
	Overall	4.00	1.171	A

Legend: VI–Verbal Interpretation 5.0-4.50 Strongly Agree (Very Evident) 4.49-3.50 Agree (Evident) 3.45-2.50 Neither Agree nor Disagree (Evident to a little extent) 2.45-1.50 Disagree (Evident to a little extent) 1.45 -1.0 Strongly Disagree (Not Evident)

Table 2 presents the respondents' perceived organizational leadership in inclusive education about transformational leadership practices. The study found that leadership by example is evident in the respondent schools (mean=4.03, SD=1.205). This approach to leadership is characteristic of a transformational leader who inspires and motivates their followers to go beyond their self-interests and contribute to a greater cause, in this case, in accepting the challenges of bringing equitable education to students of various needs and backgrounds.

Likewise, the schools promote a culture of trust and respect (mean=4.02, SD=1.210) where a leader's language is an instrument in inspiring teachers to work towards achieving the school's vision for instruction and learning that is accessible to all (mean=4.02, SD=1.198). This approach to leadership is essential for building strong relationships among co-workers and creating a supportive environment where everyone feels valued and heard. By promoting trust and respect, the schools are fostering collaboration and teamwork, which is critical for the effective implementation of inclusive education.

In addition, the survey revealed that schools employ several strategies to assist instructors, including mentorship, coaching, observation, and professional development initiatives. This discovery implies that educational institutions acknowledge the fact that teachers possess diverse requirements and preferences when it comes to their professional growth. The schools guarantee that all teachers

have access to the necessary support to properly implement inclusive education by offering a variety of support choices.

However, upon examining statement 1, which indicates the lowest average view that the school possesses a defined set of principles and vision that influences the decision-making of school administrators and instructors (mean=3.94, SD=1.216), there is a need for additional clarification. Although schools have set a vision for inclusive education following the DepEd policy framework, there may be a lack of clarity regarding the implementation processes and operationalization of this vision. For example, individuals may need to mentally imagine a comprehensive vision for a wide range of students and consider how the goal of inclusivity might be implemented. The formulation of the vision and values for implementing Individualized Education (IE), particularly concerning decision-making processes impacting students with special needs, should be carefully developed to ensure that they can be translated into clear objectives with quantifiable and attainable goals that can be easily comprehended by the main stakeholders (teachers, parents, and students).

In summary, the study's results indicate that transformational leadership was observed as a type of organizational leadership in inclusive education within the public schools examined. However, there are still some uncertainties regarding how it is implemented. According to Alianzas and Chua (2021), numerous experts have stated that success is contingent upon effective leadership. According to

Ohmae (2005), exceptional leaders can inspire and motivate their followers to accomplish remarkable outcomes. These leaders serve as catalysts in facilitating the attainment of goals and objectives. This strategy enables leaders to establish a clear vision and motivate people to realize their objectives.

Nevertheless, it is crucial to set a vision and ensure that it is comprehended and transformed into quantifiable results. The respondent schools have shown some evidence of

their dedication to promoting a culture of creativity and innovation among their teachers, establishing strong relationships built on trust and respect, and having a clear and well-defined educational vision (Aliazas et al., 2023). By doing this, the schools are progressing toward establishing an atmosphere where instructors are driven to collaborate to create an inclusive learning environment that benefits all students.

Table 3. Perceived School Readiness for Inclusive Education as to Creating Inclusive Culture

Indicators	Mean	SD	VI
1. The school is free of all forms of discrimination. (Ang paaralan ay ligtas sa lahat ng uri ng diskriminasyon.)	4.14	1.208	A
2. The expectation of participation is high for all children. (Mataas ang inaasahang pakikilahok ng lahat ng bata.)	4.13	1.211	A
3. Staff and school head work well together. (Ang mga kawani at pinuno ng paaralan ay nagtutulungan.)	4.23	1.173	A
4. Staff cooperates. (Ang mga kawani ay nagtutulungan.)	4.23	1.182	A
5. The school encourages respect for all human rights. (Hinihikayat ng paaralan ang paggalang sa lahat ng karapatang pantao.)	4.27	1.177	A
6. Children are valued equally. (Ang mga bata ay pantay-pantay na pinahahalagahan.)	4.24	1.179	A
7. Staff and children respect each other. (Ang mga kawani at bata ay nagpapakita ng paggalang sa isa't- isa.)	4.27	1.164	A
8. Everyone is welcomed. (Ang bawat isa ay malugod na tinatanggap.)	4.28	1.181	A
9. The school encourages respect for all human rights. (Hinihikayat ng paaralan ang paggalang sa lahat ng karapatang pantao.)	4.28	1.194	A
10. Inclusion is viewed as increasing participation for all. (Inaasahan ang pakikilahok ng lahat.)	4.24	1.185	A
11. The expectation of participation is high for all children. (Mataas ang inaasahang pakikilahok ng lahat ng bata.)	4.22	1.177	A
12. The school develops shared inclusive values. (Ang paaralan ay nagpapaunlad sa mga kaugnay na pagpapahalaga.)	4.24	1.168	A
13. The school and local communities develop each other. (Ang paaralan at mga lokal na pamayanan ay magkatuwang sa pagpapaunlad ng bawat isa.)	4.21	1.166	A
14. Staff link what happens in school to children's lives at home. (Naiuugnay ng kawani ang nangyayari sa paaralan sa buhay ng mga bata sa kanilang tahanan.)	4.18	1.188	A
Overall	4.22	1.152	A

Legend: VI–Verbal Interpretation 5.0-4.50 Strongly Agree (Very Evident) 4.49-3.50 Agree (Evident) 3.45-2.50 Neither Agree nor Disagree (Evident to a little extent) 2.45-1.50 Disagree (Evident to a little extent) 1.45 -1.0 Strongly Disagree (Not Evident)

Table 3 displays schools' perceived level of preparedness for inclusive education, specifically in terms of establishing an inclusive culture. The study's results suggest that the participants regard schools as having a hospitable atmosphere (mean=4.28, SD=1.181) that fosters a culture of human rights (mean=4.28, SD=1.194). This implies that the school has established a conducive atmosphere where students, teachers, and parents experience a sense of belonging, approval, and appreciation. Facilitating a sense of belonging and connectedness within the school community

can significantly influence kids' academic and social-emotional growth. Furthermore, there is mutual respect between the personnel and children within the school setting. This signifies that the school has established a culture in which mutual respect is encouraged and maintained. By fostering a secure and nurturing learning atmosphere, children are more likely to feel at ease expressing themselves and actively participating in the learning process.

In addition, the school promotes the value of upholding all fundamental human rights. This signifies that the school is dedicated to fostering diversity, fairness, and inclusivity and highly regards the distinct identities and experiences of all its students and staff. This fosters a culture in which students are empowered to speak for themselves and others, catalyzing good social transformation.

The respondents' perception clearly demonstrates school preparation for inclusive education, particularly in fostering an inclusive culture. The average score was 4.22, with a standard deviation of 1.152. Nevertheless, it is worth mentioning that certain areas for development need to be identified in certain aspects, as indicated by the lowest average view, specifically regarding the high expectation of participation for all children (mean=4.13, SD=1.211).

The collection of participation data has posed a recurring challenge in achieving inclusivity. The Department of Social Welfare reported that in 2019, around 60% of Filipino children with disabilities were not attending school. Furthermore, the 2020 study conducted by the Council for the Welfare of Children Sub-Committee on Children with Disabilities highlighted the significant issue of being unable to obtain educational services and learning materials. The limited involvement of learners with disabilities is hindered by a range of obstacles, primarily stemming from economic hardships experienced by households or a lack of accessibility to

educational institutions (Mori, 2015). According to Garcia and Reyes (2018), the infrastructure in the Philippines, including schools, roads, and transportation systems, is often not designed to accommodate individuals with disabilities, particularly those with limited mobility. Rguindin et al. reported that the country should enhance its efforts in building more inclusive spaces for those with disabilities.

The achievement of educational equality, as encapsulated by the principle of "education for all," is more likely to be successful if it is implemented through a nationwide system and inclusive schools that embrace diversity and strive to provide high-quality education to all individuals as outlined by Shaeffer (2019). The United Nations Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (United Nations, 2008) emphasized the importance of inclusive education. According to the convention, inclusive education involves a fundamental policy, practice, and culture change within educational settings. It requires the ability to cater to individual students' diverse needs and identities and a commitment to eliminating any obstacles hindering this possibility. Based on this survey, it can be deduced that schools are widely seen as effectively implementing inclusive education. However, a significant amount of work still has to be accomplished, particularly in increasing student engagement, eradicating discrimination, and fostering collaboration between schools, families, and communities.

Table 4. Perceived School Readiness for Inclusive Education as to Constructing Curricula for All Learning

	Indicators	Mean	SD	VI
1.	Children learn about ethics, power, and government. (<i>Ang mga bata ay natututo tungkol sa etika, kapangyarihan, at pamahalaan.</i>)	3.99	1.178	A
2.	Children investigate sources of energy. (<i>Sinisiyasat ng mga bata ang mga mapagkukunan ng enerhiya.</i>)	3.99	1.187	A
3.	Children investigate the importance of water. (<i>Sinisiyasat ng mga bata ang kahalagahan ng tubig.</i>)	4.06	1.182	A
4.	Children study life on earth. (<i>Ang mga bata ay nag-aaral ng buhay sa mundo.</i>)	4.02	1.207	A
5.	Children find out about housing and the built environment. (<i>Tinutuklas ng mga bata ang tungkol sa pabahay at sa mga itinayo sa kapaligiran</i>)	3.98	1.182	A
6.	Children study the clothing and decoration of the body. (<i>Pinag-aaralan ng mga bata ang damit at dekorasyon ng katawan.</i>)	4.02	1.189	A
7.	Children engage with and create, literature arts, and music. (<i>Ang mga bata ay nakikilahok at lumikha ng sining, panitikan, at musika.</i>)	4.06	1.193	A
8.	Children consider how and why people move around their locality and the world. (<i>Isinasaalang-alang ng mga bata kung paano at bakit nagpapalipat-lipat ang mga tao sa kanilang lokalidad at sa buong mundo.</i>)	4.01	1.178	A
9.	Children learn about health and relationships. (<i>Natututuhan ng mga bata ang tungkol sa kalusugan at mga relasyon.</i>)	4.07	1.179	A
10.	Children learn about communication and technology. (<i>Ang mga bata ay natututo tungkol sa pakikipagtalastasan at teknolohiya.</i>)	4.05	1.184	A
11.	Children explore the cycle of food production and consumption. (<i>Ang mga bata ay nakapagsaliksik tungkol sa siklo ng produksyon at pagkonsumo ng pagkain.</i>)	4.02	1.170	A
12.	Children learn about the earth, the solar system, and the universe. (<i>Natutuhan ng</i>	3.99	1.181	A

mga bata ang tungkol sa mundo, ang solar system, at ang sansinukob.)

13. Children learn about work and link it to the development of their interests. (<i>Natutuhan ng mga bata ang tungkol sa trabaho at naiugnay ito sa pagpapaunlad ng kanilang mga interes.</i>)	4.03	1.184	A
Overall	4.02	1.152	A

Legend: VI–Verbal Interpretation 5.0-4.50 Strongly Agree (Very Evident) 4.49-3.50 Agree (Evident) 3.45-2.50 Neither Agree nor Disagree (Evident to a little extent) 2.45-1.50 Disagree (Evident to a little extent) 1.45 -1.0 Strongly Disagree (Not Evident)

Table 4 presents the respondents' perceived school readiness for inclusive education in constructing curricula for all learning. The study findings generally suggest that the school is committed to providing an inclusive curriculum that caters to the diverse learning needs of all students (mean=4.02, SD= 1.152).

The study explicitly shown that children acquire knowledge about health and relationships, with a mean score of 4.07 and a standard deviation of 1.179. In addition, they actively participate in and produce literature, arts, and music (mean=4.06, standard deviation=1.193), explore the significance of water (mean=4.06, standard deviation=1.182), study communication technology (mean=4.05, standard deviation=1.184), and examine the characteristics of works that relate to the growth of their interests (mean=4.03, standard deviation=1.184). These responses suggest the diverse variety of learning opportunities that elementary schools' curricula offer students. Therefore, this provides opportunities for students to develop holistically, focusing on the knowledge and skills relevant to students' social-emotional well-being, preparation for future careers, and understanding of the environment, which can help students navigate the modern world's complex social and technological landscape. On the other hand, some curriculum contents garnered low agreement and thus need to be emphasized. The curriculum helping children to learn about housing and the built

environment (mean=3.98, SD=1.189), children learning about ethics, power and government (mean=3.99, SD=1.178), children investigating sources of energy (mean=3.99, SD=1.187) and children learning about the earth, the solar system and the universe (mean=3.99, SD=1.184). It can be inferred from this that certain aspects of the curriculum require additional emphasis. Inclusive education refers to the practice of placing all students, regardless of any challenges or learning disabilities they may have, in age-appropriate general education classes. The goal of inclusive education is to provide these students with high-quality instruction, interventions, and supports that will help them succeed in the core curriculum (Alquraini & Gut, 2012).

This means that the curriculum offered to them, like that offered in the regular classroom, encompasses learning in all areas, including those that will help them become literate Filipinos who can participate fully in society, such as natural, environmental and social sciences.

In general, the respondent schools shown a clear preparedness to incorporate inclusive education into their curriculum development for all students. Nevertheless, certain elements must be incorporated and addressed for the curriculum to accommodate the varied learning requirements of all pupils and foster comprehensive development.

Table 5. Perceived School Readiness for Inclusive Education Implementation as to Orchestrating Learning

Indicators	Mean	SD	VI
1. Children learn from each other. (Ang mga bata ay natututo sa bawat isa.)	4.05	1.129	A
2. Learning activities encourage the participation of all learners. (Ang mga gawain sa pagkatuto ay humihimok sa pakikilahok ng lahat ng mga mag-aaral.)	4.12	1.141	A
3. Children are actively involved in their learning. (Ang mga bata ay aktibong nakikilahok sa kanilang pagkatuto.)	4.14	1.163	A
4. Assessment encourages the achievements of all children. (Hinihikayat ng pagtatasa ang mga natutunan ng lahat ng mga bata.)	4.14	1.178	A
5. Learning activities are planned with all children in mind. (Ang mga gawain sa pagkatuto ay binabalangkas batay o ayon sa lahat ng mga bata.)	4.11	1.169	A
6. Staff plan, teach and review together. (Ang mga kawani ay sama-	4.11	1.168	A

samang nagpapalano, nagtuturo at nagsusuri.)

Overall

4.11

1.134

A

Legend: VI–Verbal Interpretation 5.0-4.50 Strongly Agree (Very Evident) 4.49-3.50 Agree (Evident) 3.45-2.50 Neither Agree nor Disagree (Evident to a little extent) 2.45-1.50 Disagree (Evident to a little extent) 1.45 -1.0 Strongly Disagree (Not Evident)

Table 5 displays the participants' perception of their preparedness for implementing inclusive education in organizing learning. In general, the participants viewed the preparedness of schools for inclusive education as the effective coordination of learning, as shown by a mean score of 4.11 and a standard deviation of 1.134. Therefore, the schools are adopting inclusive education.

More precisely, the data showed that children actively participated in their education, with a mean score of 4.14 and a standard deviation of 1.163. This indicates that the school successfully offered students chances to participate in practical and experienced learning experiences that stimulate their curiosity and creativity. Active engagement in the classroom is sometimes referred to as participation in collaborative learning groups (Braxton et al., 2000), where students can form a close-knit community of supportive peers. It is crucial in inclusive educational environments as it can facilitate the formation of peer relationships, which subsequently aid pupils in assimilating into social groupings. These elements facilitate contact, involvement, and collaboration, crucial for promoting effective learning (Harkaitz et al., 2020).

Furthermore, the study revealed that the participants believed that assessments promote the success of all children, including those with special needs and those without, as indicated by a mean score of 4.14 and a standard deviation of 1.163. The concept of 'adapted assessment' aptly describes this notion, referring to an assessment that involves suitable changes and adjustments to provide students with special educational needs in the general education curriculum with a higher likelihood of effective participation in assessments. The demand for modified evaluation is a prominent aspect of the standards-based education reforms that currently dominate global educational and political discussions (Mitchell, 2015).

Nevertheless, adjustments and alternate assessments, which are considered alterations, should not be interpreted literally. It is crucial to emphasize that when making accommodations for assessments in an inclusive classroom, the specific needs of each student should be considered. These accommodations may include granting additional time to complete the assessment, providing large print or Braille versions of test papers for visually impaired students, or allowing transcribed responses for students who are unable to write. Essentially, evaluation promotes academic success for all children, including those who are disadvantaged, without granting them

an unjust advantage over their peers who do not have learning disabilities or special educational requirements.

Although the implementation of inclusive education in facilitating learning was generally observed, it is important to highlight that there is a relatively low level of agreement on statement 1, which states that children learn from each other (mean=4.05, SD=1.129). This implies that even while the learning activities are done in groups, teachers should create projects that benefit all participants equally, regardless of their limitations.

While research suggests that the cooperation between typical students and students with intellectual disability (ID) during learning activities can have a beneficial effect on the progress of students with ID, this assertion may not universally hold. Facilitating social inclusion for all students has been proposed by establishing meaningful social interactions via collaborative learning. Nevertheless, knowledge co-creation can be ineffective in peer groups that include students with varying abilities, including those with and without special educational needs (SEN) (Niemi, 2022). For example, even though students with special educational needs (SEN) made appropriate on-task initiations, their contributions were disregarded, dismissed, invalidated, manipulated, or diminished regarding their role as helpers. Although the teachers have consistently promoted collaborative work through joint activities, task negotiation, and ensuring equal participation of students with special educational needs or learning disabilities, the challenge persists.

As to the Center for Studies in Inclusive Education (CSIE), effectively implementing inclusive practices in education necessitates planning teaching strategies that include the learning needs of all students (Booth & Ainscow, 2002). This study observed that elementary schools demonstrate a strong dedication to creating a learning environment that addresses the different learning requirements of all kids and fosters active learning, cooperation, and equitable access to educational opportunities. Nevertheless, expanding further and exploring ambiguous aspects of implementation remains necessary.

Table 12. Test of Relationship between Organizational Leadership and Inclusive Education Implementation

Organizational Leadership in Inclusive Education	Inclusive Education Implementation			
	Creating Inclusive Culture	Constructing Curricular for All	Orchestrating Learning	Overall Implementation
Leadership Roles and Responsibilities	.777**	.781**	.787**	.811**
Transformational Leadership Practices	.830**	.778**	.824**	.841**
Overall Organizational Leadership	.836**	.812**	.839**	.860**

***. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).*

Table 12 examines the correlation between organizational leadership and inclusive education. The study's findings indicate a strong association between organizational leadership and the implementation of inclusive education. This correlation is evident in the establishment of an inclusive culture ($r = .836$), the development of curricula for all students ($r = .812$), and the facilitation of learning ($r = .839$). These findings indicate that school leaders who assume inclusive leadership duties and responsibilities are more likely to effectively guide their schools in adopting inclusive education. Establishing a healthy school culture, or ethos, in an inclusive educational institution entails formulating and executing objectives that align with its members' collective values, beliefs, attitudes, traditions, and behavioral standards, particularly those in leadership positions (Mitchelle, 2015). Thus, leadership roles must be exercised to create an inclusive school culture. These roles could come in forms like defining the school's philosophy and inclusion goals and having these promulgated in different avenues such as school publications, parent-community conferences, consultations with external stakeholders or even during casual conversations. Leaders may likewise find ways by which 'promoters' of inclusion and inclusive practices may be given recognition, whether formal or informal. Similarly, inclusive leaders must acknowledge the significance of allocating sufficient resources to the school and guarantee that these resources, when accessible, are dispersed fairly and utilized efficiently.

The UN Convention on the Rights of People with Disabilities defines inclusive education as encompassing not only learners with disabilities but all learners with specific educational requirements, regardless of their backgrounds. Further, the organizational leadership roles of a principal also relate to creating curricula suitable for all learners. This may suggest that for inclusive education to be implemented and succeed in its implementation, school heads may need to recognize the need for evolving curricula that will benefit all students, the need to change or update textbooks and other learning resources or implement innovative pedagogies and

assessments that comes with likely have a positive impact on learners' achievements and adjustments in the mainstream. The study also discovered a strong correlation between the adoption of transformational leadership approaches and the successful implementation of inclusive education to foster an inclusive culture ($r = .830^{**}$), develop comprehensive curricula ($r = .778$), and facilitate effective learning ($r = .824$). These findings indicate that school administrators who demonstrate transformational leadership strategies are more inclined to adopt inclusive education effectively. Transformational leadership encompasses the act of inspiring and encouraging people, as well as giving intellectual stimulation and developing customized consideration.

Principals and assistant principals, referred to as school leaders, have crucial responsibilities in guaranteeing the achievement of inclusive special education in the schools under their supervision (Romanuck Murphy, 2018). Transformational leadership enhances productivity in the context of inclusive education. It enables students to concentrate on their areas of expertise while facilitating teachers to establish significant connections with all students in the classroom. Inclusive education is best exemplified by empowering teachers to devise suitable motivational strategies and teaching approaches, displaying reverence for the varied cultural backgrounds of their students, and making efforts to cater to the learning requirements of individuals with learning disabilities and obstacles (El-Jabali, 2019).

The transformation style also underscores the importance of a collective vision directing all organization members, including teachers, principals, parents, students, and other stakeholders. The transformational leader will establish the vision based on the anticipated results of the inclusive schools. Nevertheless, the leader must customize all the procedures to attain the objectives, consequently resulting in the cultivation of triumph.

The significant association between organizational leadership and the implementation of inclusive education

underscores the crucial role of effective leadership in establishing an inclusive and equitable learning environment. Schools led by competent leaders who assume leadership duties and responsibilities and demonstrate transformational leadership practices are more inclined to effectively implement inclusive education methods that address the various learning requirements of all students.

Effective implementation of inclusive education policies relies heavily on organizational leadership. Avramidis and Norwich (2002) conducted a study that concluded that good school leadership is crucial for the successful implementation of inclusive education strategies. According to Aliazas et al. (2021), leaders who assume leadership roles and demonstrate transformational leadership practices are likelier to establish an inclusive school culture that encourages cooperation and enhances student accomplishment.

Furthermore, a separate study by Beycioglu & Kondakci (2014) emphasizes the significance of leadership in implementing inclusive education policies. According to the author, leaders dedicated to diversity and equity are more inclined to establish a school culture that encourages collaboration and enhances student accomplishment. In addition, Zimmerman et al. (2019) discovered that school leaders who demonstrate distributed leadership techniques have a higher probability of effectively implementing

inclusive education strategies. The authors contend that implementing distributed leadership techniques, characterized by delegating leadership tasks and decision-making to other stakeholders, is crucial in establishing an inclusive school culture that encourages cooperation and enhances student accomplishment.

Moreover, Hsieh's (2021) study revealed that proficient school leadership is crucial in successfully executing inclusive education policies in Taiwan. The authors contend that leaders who advocate for inclusivity and equity, offer continuous professional development opportunities for staff, and foster a positive school culture are more prone to implement inclusive education approaches effectively. The results indicate that proficient organizational leadership is crucial for successfully implementing inclusive education approaches. Leaders who assume leadership positions and duties, demonstrate transformative leadership strategies, advocate for inclusivity and fairness, offer continuous professional growth opportunities for staff, and foster a favorable school environment are more inclined to effectively implement inclusive education practices that address the varied learning requirements of all students.

Table 14. Regression Analysis of Organizational Leadership on Inclusive Education Implementation

Model Summary						
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate		
1	.860 ^a	.740	.739	.564078449762176		
ANOVA						
	Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	367.166	1	367.166	1153.939	.000 ^b
	Residual	129.183	406	.318		
	Total	496.348	407			

a. Dependent Variable: Inclusive Education Implementation

b. Predictors: (Constant), Organizational Leadership

Coefficients						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.825	.101		8.171	.000
	Organizational Leadership	.835	.025	.860	33.970	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Inclusive Education Implementation

The research also showed that the independent factors explained 73.9% of the difference in scores related to implementing inclusive education. This implies that the variations observed in implementing inclusive education can be ascribed to the collective impact of organizational leadership.

Moreover, the data reveal that the independent variable, namely organizational leadership, is a good predictor of inclusive education implementation. Consequently, a positive correlation exists between elevated levels of corporate leadership and increased levels of inclusive education implementation. The correlation between these characteristics and the adoption of inclusive education implies that the successful execution of inclusive education methods is more probable when businesses possess proficient leadership. Moreover, the stepwise multiple regression analysis results offer proof of the substantial impact of organizational leadership on the implementation of inclusive education. These findings emphasize the significance of prioritizing these elements in endeavors to improve and advocate for inclusive education methods. Through the enhancement of organizational leadership, educational institutions can successfully integrate inclusive education and establish a conducive atmosphere that promotes the achievement and welfare of every student.

Inclusive education has emerged as a global priority in recent years, ensuring equitable access to education for all children, irrespective of their various backgrounds, abilities, or impairments. Efficient organizational leadership is pivotal in successfully executing inclusive education in public elementary schools. School leaders' attitudes, ideas, and actions substantially impact how teachers and staff perceive and implement inclusive education. James (2014) conducted a study that found that school principals who possessed expertise, assisted, and fostered collaboration concerning inclusive education had a beneficial influence on their instructors' inclusive teaching methods. Moreover, it was shown that principals who included parents, students, and community members in inclusive education achieved greater success in its implementation.

In a similar vein, Deng (2020) conducted a study examining the correlation between principals' leadership styles and the execution of inclusive education in primary schools in New Zealand. The study revealed that principals who embraced a transformational leadership approach, encouraging and motivating their team to collaborate towards a shared objective, had a beneficial influence on their teachers' views and implementation of inclusive education. The findings indicate a strong correlation between organizational leadership

and the successful implementation of inclusive education in public elementary schools.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn.

1. There is a significant relationship between organizational leadership in public elementary schools and all the dimensions of implementing inclusive education.
2. Organizational leadership significantly predicts the extent of inclusive education implementation.

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